

Human-Robot Collaboration during the Execution of Structured Co-manipulation Tasks

Jonathan Cacace, Riccardo Caccavale, Alberto Finzi, Riccardo Grieco, and Vincenzo Lippiello
 Dipartimento di Ingegneria Elettrica e Tecnologie dell'Informazione (DIETI)

Università degli Studi di Napoli "Federico II"

Naples, Italy

{jonathan.cacace, riccardo.caccavale, alberto.finzi, riccardo.grieco, vincenzo.lippiello}@unina.it

Abstract—In this work, we consider human-robot collaboration during the execution of structured co-manipulation tasks to be interactively accomplished exploiting the human physical guidance. In this scenario, human interventions are continuously assessed by the robotic system to infer whether the human guidance is consistent with respect to the shared plan. On the other hand, the estimated intentions associated with the human interventions are also exploited by the robot to on-line regulate its cooperative behavior in the context of the shared task. For this purpose, the collaborative robot can adjust tasks/subtasks, or motions, while regulating its compliance with respect to the operator's guidance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Collaborative robots enable humans and robots to safely work in a shared workspace during the execution of joint activities and tasks exploiting their complementary abilities. In these settings, the activities of humans and robots should be monitored, coordinated, and suitably orchestrated with respect to the task structure and the human guidance. In particular, we consider a scenario where a human operator interacts with a robotic arm through physical hand-guided interventions in order to accomplish hierarchically structured collaborative activities. In these contexts, human inputs can be associated with different purposes, like slightly adjusting robot motions, changing the target of the actions, or using the manipulator as a passive tool. The intentions conveyed with these physical interventions are to be continuously interpreted by the robotic system with respect to the planned activities and motions, while the robot behaviour should be adapted accordingly. Specifically, when the human guidance is aligned with respect to the planned activities, these are maintained along with trajectories and targets. Otherwise, the robotic system may switch tasks, change targets, and adjust trajectories, while suitably regulating the robot's compliance with respect to human's hand-guidance. To address these issues, we leverage the framework proposed in [1] - [3], which exploits supervisory attention and contention scheduling to monitor human behaviours and suitably orchestrate multiple hierarchically structured tasks with respect to the interpreted human interventions.

In the proposed system, collaborative task execution occurs while simultaneously interpreting the human interventions in the context of the planned activities. Based on the operational state and the environmental stimuli, the supervisory system

Fig. 1. Left: system architecture. Right: executive system.

enables possible subtasks, targets and trajectories, which are continuously evaluated by intention recognition processes.

II. COLLABORATIVE HUMAN-ROBOT MANIPULATION

The architecture of the collaborative system consists of two main control layers (Fig. 1 left). The *High-Level Control System* (HLC) is a deliberative layer responsible for task generation, decomposition, orchestration, and interaction, while the *Low-Level Control System* (LLC) manages the current execution of the primitive operations selected by the HLC while maintaining the robotic system compliant with respect to the human interventions. The *Executive System* manages the execution of multiple collaborative tasks considering both environmental changes and human activities. During task execution, the human operator can physically interact with the robot and these interventions are simultaneously interpreted at the different layers of the architecture. Depending on the task, the environmental context, and the human interventions, the Executive System proposes a set of primitive operations (*Behaviors*) that compete for the execution (*Contention*). Each proposed behaviour is associated with a target position (*Target*) and an activation value. The latter representing an attentional weight. The *Target estimation* module generates a trajectory (*Trajectory Planner*) for each proposed target and assesses it (*Intention Estimation*) considering the current human guidance in order to estimate the most aligned with respect to the human interventions. Finally, the LLC implements a *Shared Controller* aimed at mixing the inputs generated by the human

operator with the ones needed to perform robot motion (*Shared force*). An (*Admittance Controller*) integrates the human and the robot guidance.

A. Executive System

The Executive System is depicted in Fig. 1 right and it is responsible for task monitoring and execution (See [5]). It is decomposed into an *Attentional Executive System* module that manages the execution of hierarchically structured tasks along with the associated activations and an *Attentional Behavior-based System* module that collects the active robot processes, each associated with an activation value. In this system, the *Long Term Memory* (LTM) collects the system procedural knowledge, i.e., the tasks. The *Working Memory* (WM) is a data structure that collects hierarchically decomposed tasks instantiated and allocated for execution. The task set in the WM along with the associated state variables characterizes the current execution state of the system. The WM is represented by an annotated rooted directed graph whose nodes represent allocated tasks/subtasks and the edges are parental relations among subtasks. Finally, the leaves in the WM structure correspond to *attentional behaviors* devoted to the execution of sensorimotor processes. Finally, a Behavior-based System collects all the allocated, active, and concrete behaviors which compete for the execution. Behaviors can be marked as *enabled*, if the associated precondition in WM along with the ancestors' preconditions are satisfied, *disabled* otherwise. An enabled behavior is *accomplished* if its postcondition is satisfied. A *contention scheduling* mechanism is used to solve conflicts generated by the contemporary execution of multiple behaviors. When a conflict arises, following a winner-takes-all approach, the behavior associated with a higher activation value is selected for exclusive access to a contended resource. In the WM, the activation value of a node is the weighted sum of all contributions for that node:

$$\mu_b = \sum_i w_{i,b} c_{i,b}, \quad (1)$$

where contributions $c_{i,b}$ can be either inherited from the connected nodes (with $i \neq b$) in the WM structure (top-down) or generated by the node itself ($i = b$) from external or internal stimuli (bottom-up), while $w_{i,b}$ are the contribution-specific weights. This way, given a shared resource or variable v and the set of competing behaviors $B(v)$ for that variable, the behavior acquiring v is $b_{win} = \arg \max_{b \in B(v)} (\mu_b)$.

B. Classification and Regulations

Nodes' activations in the WM can be influenced by the following elements. The *task-based*, the *Human-based*, and the *Accessibility-based* influences. They consider the execution of the task, the human input and the environmental influences, respectively. These elements are combined considering the following equation.

$$c_{i,i} = m_h \cdot h_i + m_a \cdot a_i \quad (2)$$

with $m_a, m_h \in [1, 0]$ and $m_a = 1 - m_h$. Such a weighted sum is exploited to mediate between accessibility and human

guidance. Finally, the *Accessibility-based influence* (a_i) is calculated based on the state of the environment and emphasizes enabled nodes whose motion targets are more accessible (e.g., closer). This influence drives the robot towards the closest location where an operation can be performed (target), while the *human-based influence* induces the robot to move towards the target pointed by the operator guidance. Depending on the weights' balance in Equation 2 we can considered different operative conditions. When $m_h \gg m_a$ the system runs in *Human-guided* mode. In this case, the robot is more prone to follow the human guidance rather than possible alternatives enabled by the plan and suggested by the environment. With $m_a \gg m_h$, the *Target-guided* mode is activated. In this case, the robot tends to act according to the plan guidance and the environmental stimuli, rather than following the operator inputs. Finally, with $m_a \approx m_h$, the robot works in *Balanced* mode. In this case, the system is not biased towards accessible targets or human guidance, but the robotic behavior is equally sensitive to both of them.

C. Operator Intention Estimation

Human intention estimation is performed exploiting Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) based on LSTM nodes which evaluates human physical interventions on the robot with respect to targets and related trajectories (see [4]). Such interventions are classified by the network as *Concorde* (when human guidance follow the trajectory), *Deviation Concorde* (the operator guidance modifies the trajectory without changing the active target), *Opposite* (hand guidance moves the robot against the current motion) and *Deviation Opposite* (the operator hand guidance aims at switching the current target). The input of the network is represented by an *interaction snapshot* made up by the human force magnitude $\|F_t\|$, the angle between human force direction and planned motion $d_p = \angle(\vec{d}_a, \vec{d}_p)$, and the distance between the position of the end-effector, and the closest point of the trajectory $d_h = \|X_p - X_c\|$. 4 nodes corresponding to the possible classes make up the output layer.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The research leading to these results has supported by the HARMONY EU project (grant 101017008) and PRIN PRINBOT project (grant 20172HHNK5_002).

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Caccavale, A. Finzi, "Flexible Task Execution and Attentional Regulations in Human-Robot Interaction," *Trans. on Cognitive and Development Systems*, vol. 9, pp. 68–79, 2017.
- [2] R. Caccavale, M. Saveriano, A. Finzi, D. Lee, "Kinesthetic teaching and attentional supervision of structured tasks in human-robot interaction," *Autonomous Robots*, vol. 43, pp. 1291–1307, 2019.
- [3] R. Caccavale, A. Finzi, "Learning attentional regulations for structured tasks execution in robotic cognitive control," *Autonomous Robots*, vol. 43, pp. 2229–2243, 2019.
- [4] J. Cacace, R. Caccavale, A. Finzi and V. Lippiello, "Interactive Plan Execution during Human-Robot Cooperative Manipulation," *IFAC*, vol. 51, pp. 500–505, 2018.
- [5] J. Cacace, R. Caccavale, A. Finzi, R. Grieco, "Combining human guidance and structured task execution during physical human-robot collaboration," *J Intell Manuf*, pp. 1572–8145, 2022.